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An Appraisal Of The Contribution Made By The Government Toward The Development On The Local Games To The Development Of The Society

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ABSTRACT

The development and the overall contributions of traditional games and sports in social integration and cohesion within the society cannot be underestimated. Traditional games have been seen as a unifying factor in any given society, from simple to complex. Traditional games have been one of the cultural practices that bring about and improve social cohesion and social integration in the society. In some cases, traditional games serve as facilitator or a tool for peace and reconciliation initiative at every stratum of the society. Traditional games and sports are often identified by the traditional rulers as a field of actions that improve the spirit of unity and promote intercultural understanding and mutual respect within the groups and communities in the society. Many traditional games and sports have been durable parts of cultural identity and diversity; often they have lasted in similar forms for thousands of years and been the backbone of diverse communities. Therefore, this paper which is mainly literature review, theoretically based and conceptual, explores the roles of traditional games and sports on social integration and social cohesion. Literature used in the paper were sourced from secondary sources like journal, books, conference papers, seminal papers and newspapers.

Keywords: Traditional Games, Tradition Sports, Social Integration, government

INTRODUCTION

Local cultural games play vital roles in providing sense of identity for the rural communities and residents. Local games are games that are local because they are based on the cultural practices of the people of the region. In north western Nigeria, such local or cultural games are many and they provide tremendous socio-economic impacts on the region. This identity facilitates common understandings, traditions, and values, all central to the identifications of plans of action to improve wellbeing of the rural communities particularly in North Western Nigeria. In most societies, Cultural games form the backbone of a community or the society and further community spirit, bring and bind people together and instil a sense of pride. Most of these cultural games are expression of indigenous cultures and ways of life that contribute to the common identity of humanity, have already disappeared and those that have survived are threatened by imminent disappearance and extinction under the combined effect of globalization and harmonization of the rich diversity of world sport heritage. Playing these cultural games of *Sharo*, *Dambe*, *Kokawa*, *Langa* and *Doro* especially in the North western Nigerian societies help players and

spectators to hear news, get information and keep abreast of local gossip, while talking about something around the game. Indeed, around the game, someone takes the opportunity to recall outstanding debts. If one player is the debtor, makes the excuse that they are playing at the moment and cannot speak, thus postponing the payment of the debt. In another development, these cultural games reduce stress because the players and the spectators crack jokes which take away boredom and fatigue. These cultural games also help to foster unity in the neighbourhoods. This is because the games allow both the players and the spectators to mingle together and crack jokes thus serving as an avenue to foster unity. At the venues of the game, matters of concern to an individual or the community may be brought up for discussion and appropriate solution is quickly found.

These cultural games however train individuals to be tolerant and forbear, because a leading competitor and the spectators could be taunting the impending loser judging from the flow of the game, the impending loser must have the courage to bear the jesting and refuse to lose composure. It encourages players to device means to solve problems. It affords the players the opportunity to think faster under any situation they may find themselves. The research will examine the local games cultural, economic and political contribution to the national development and explore how it influence the confidence of rural communities of North Western Nigeria having for coming together to address specific needs and problems

Statement of the Problem

This role of local games tend to be hidden and largely ignored in government and policy makers in Nigeria. North western Nigeria, which is predominantly Hausa, Fulanis, and other tribes, have benefited from some of these local games silently. Therefore, the problem is how do we identify the impact of some these local games like *Dambe, Sharo, Langa, kokawa, and Doro* to the economic development and social cohesion?

REVIEW OF RELETED LITERATURE

Traditional games are used for conservational, protection and safeguarding of social-cultural practices and social integration (Ambretti, Palmbro & Elias, 2019). Traditional games and sports can be used to control the rate of frustration in the society because of the ability to integrate the frustrated; hence this will reduce the rate of suicide in the society. Traditional games and sports have the impact emotions on the social-relation aspects and regulating social life. Emotional intelligence is formulated as the ability to reason about emotions and the ability to use emotions and emotional knowledge to enhance thought. Mayer and Salovey (1997) defined emotional intelligence as the ability to perceive accurately, appraise and express emotion, the ability to access and/or generate feelings when they facilitate thought, the ability to understand emotion and emotional knowledge, and the ability to regulate emotions to promote emotional and intellectual growth. Salovey and Grewal (2005) further said that it consists of four different parts; perceiving, using understanding and managing emotions. The first part is the ability to detect and identify emotions in cultural artefacts faces, voices, also in other humans. The second part is related to cognitive functions like the ability to use emotions in order to support, for example, problem-solving. The third part is the ability to realise complicated relationships among emotions and to understand the language of emotions and the fourth parts relates to the ability to regulate own emotions as well as emotion in others.

Traditional games and sports can be used to integrate all the ethnical components of the society. Nigeria being a multi ethnic country can use traditional sports to integrate the various ethnic groups and this can reduce friction and inter-ethnic conflicts in Nigerian societies. Rizvi (2009) posited that as members of a local community and a changing global society, we must create meaningful relationships with people from other cultures, histories, religious, and ethnic background. Traditional games and sports is an arena where people from different strata in a society meet. Traditional games and sports play an important role for social cohesion by providing opportunities for meetings and exchange between people of different gender, abilities and nationality or from different cultures, thereby strengthening the culture of living together

This sub-heading deals with the review of related empirical studies that are directly or indirectly relevant to the present study. The reviewed studies among others include those of Ambretti, Palmbro & Elias (2019). Traditional Games Body Movement carried out a study on the contributions of Community toward the development cultural games and the Stakeholders in CO-production of cultural games in Nigeria. The paper investigates the contributions of community stakeholders in the co-production of good cultural games in Nigeria.

Research Objectives

- 1 Find out how government can use these games to foster peace and harmony in the region
- 2 Identify some of the challenges being faced by the players of these games and Proffer solutions to these challenges

Research Question

1. Are there any contribution made by the government toward the development on these local games to the development of the society.
- 2 How did local cultural games influence cultural development in our community?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section deals with the procedure to be used in carrying out the research. The procedures will be treated under the following sub-headings: Research Design, Population of the study, Sample and Sampling Techniques, Instrument for Data Collection, Validation of the Instrument, Reliability of the Instrument, Procedure for data collection and analysis.

Population of the Study

The population of the study is 894 across the 5 local games . This is distributed as follows Sharo (180), Dambe (179), Kokawa (178)Doro (174), and Langa (178). Also 466 traditional leaders will be interview in Sokoto (70), Zamfara (70), Kebbi (65), Katsina (70), Jigawa (51) Kano (70), and Kaduna(70). Similarly , politicians, religious leaders and players of these local games will be interacted with in the different state .

Sample and Sampling Techniques

There are seven state in zone ie North –Western Nigeria namely, Sokoto, Kebbi, Zamfara, Katsina, Kano, Kaduna and Jigawa. The work intend to cover few state out of 7. This these states are Sokoto, (Sokoto north and south, TAMBUWAL, Illela and Tureta), Zamfara (Gusau, Talata mafara, Tsafe.), Kebbi (Argungu, Birnin kebbi, Gwandu, Jega, Yauri), Katsina (Katsina, Daura, Funtuwa.) .

Research Instrument

The researchers self constructed questionnaire will be used for the study titled “Questionnaires on Assessing the Contributions of cultural games in North Western Nigeria. It will have a total of 25 items in clusters (A,B, C D and E) based on the five research questions formulated for the study. The questionnaires will be structured along four points rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Strongly Disagree (SD) and Disagree (D).

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument will be validated by two expert from school of art and social sciences Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto State.

Reliability of the Instrument

In order to ascertain the reliability of instruments, using six research assistants, 60 copies of the instrument will be tested in non selected LGAs the internal consistency of the instrument will be established for the study using Cronbach Alpha. The extent is to determine whether the instrument is consistent in measuring what it is expected to measure in terms of its clarity and comprehensiveness.

Method of Data Collection

For the purpose of data collection, the 466 questionnaire will be administered by researchers with the assistant of six research assistants to be employed for the study.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question 4: *Are there any contribution made by the government toward the development on these local games to the development of the society.*

The answer to this research question was obtained from items 19-24 of Local cultural games Questionnaire (LCGQ) and presented in table 4.

Table 4: Are there any contribution made by the government toward the development on these local games to the development of the society. N= (378)

S/N	Item Statement	Agree		Disagree		Remark
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%	
1	Is there government intervention on local cultural games.	316	84	62	16	
2	Government organize local cultural games in your community.	306	81	72	19	
3	Government give prize to the local games champions.	262	69	116	31	
4	Lack of government fund affects organizing local cultural game in the state.	300	79	78	21	
5	Government publicize local cultural games in the state.	311	82	67	18	
6	Government use cultural games as source of revenue .	234	62	144	38	

Source: Field Work

Key: A= Agree; D=Disagree N= (378)

Table 4 shows the extent to which, many contribution made by the government toward the development on these local games to the development of the society. 316 of the respondents representing 84% largely agreed that Is there government intervention on local cultural games, 306 representing 81% of the respondents agree that Government organize local cultural games in your community. Similarly, 262 respondents representing 69% agree that Government give prize to the local games champions. While 300, 311 and 234 of the respondents representing 79%, 82% and 62% agree that Lack of government fund affects organizing local cultural game in the state, Government publicize local cultural games in the state.

Research Question 5: How did local cultural games influence cultural development in our community.

The answer to this research question was obtained from items 25-29 of Local cultural games Questionnaire (LCGQ) and presented in table 5.

Table 5: How did local cultural games influence cultural development in our community N= (378)

S/N	Item Statement	Agree		Disagree		Remark
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%	
1	Are you interested in the local cultural games	128	34	250	66	Rejected
2	Do you have support from government to organize local cultural games in the state	167	44	211	56	Rejected
3	Including local cultural games to national tournament can facilitate cultural development in the society.	163	43	215	57	Rejected
4	Do you observed cultural games in your community.	171	45	207	55	Rejected

Source: Field Work

Key: A= Agree; D=Disagree; N= (378)

Table 5 shows the extent at How did local cultural games influence cultural development in our community. Specifically, 250 of the respondents representing 66% largely disagreed that Are you interested in the local cultural games. While 211 and 215 representing 56% and 57% Do you have support from government to organize local cultural games in the state respectively. Similarly, 207 respondents representing 55% do you observed cultural games in your community while 250 representing 66% of the respondents agreed are you interested in the local cultural games.

CONCLUSION

Traditional games and sports have served as promising hope and gives confidence to improve interethnic contacts and social cohesion in a society as tool for peace and reconciliation initiatives at all levels. Traditional sports and games possess core values which are compatible with the principles necessary for development and peace, such as fair play, cooperation, sharing and respect. The life skills learned through sport help empower individuals and enhance psychological well-being, such as increased resiliency, self-esteem and connections with others. These features of traditional games and sports are beneficial to people of all ages but are especially vital to the health development of young people.

RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations are made in order to encourage social integration and social cohesion in the society through traditional games

- 1 There should be writing rules for traditional games to make it recognisable internationally
- 2 There is need for the government support to the local cultural games by including them to the national tournament

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